

3D INTERPARTICLE SPACING AND RADII DISTRIBUTION OF SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS EVALUATED FROM PLANAR SECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a simulation analysis for determination of spatial interparticle distances and radii distribution of spherical inclusions from planar images of the microstructure. The analysis is based upon a correlation procedure between probability density functions of inclusions' radii and interparticle distances and their counterparts estimated from simulated cross sections of a cube containing 10.000 to 60.000 spherical inclusions. A correlation map has been established that relates 2D profiles with 3D distribution of spherical inclusions whose radii follow a Gauss distribution. Similar correlation maps can be created for constant, uniform random, Poisson and lognormal distributions of sphere radii.

INTRODUCTION

The overall mechanical properties of a disordered composite medium can differ significantly even when composites are made from identical constituent materials but processed differently. Whilst the properties of phases are fixed by their constitution, geometrical arrangements are technologically variable. Experimentally determined property values are usually presented in terms of their variation with volume fraction of the dispersed phase, which is merely a statement of the overall composition of the material rather than of its dispersion characteristics. Modelling of a microstructure has customarily been based on the assumption that the microstructure is either perfectly regular or completely random. In order to predict exactly the effective properties of disordered two-phase composite, it is necessary to know not only the phases' properties and volume fraction, but also geometrical arrangement and sizes of the phases. This paper presents a simulation analysis for determination of spatial interparticle distances and radii distribution of spherical particles from planar microscopic images of composite cross sections.

METHOD

The analysis is based upon a correlation procedure between probability density functions of three-dimensional features and its counterparts estimated from simulated cross sections of a cube containing 10.000 to 60.000 spherical inclusions. The size of the cube is 1024x1024x

Figure 1: Computer simulated cube containing a planar section.

1024 in which planar microscopic images of 512x512 are analysed, Fig. 1. The cube is larger than the analysed image in order to avoid edge effects in the spatial features. Five different distribution functions are used for the 3D sphere radii to cover most spherical size distributions which may occur in practical applications; constant, uniform random, Poisson, Gauss and lognormal distributed radii [1] - [4]. The positions of the inclusions follow a Gibbs hard-core distribution of random positions in space. For the position of the cross section in the cube A-weighted random section is used because this alone leads to unbiased estimates [1], [5], [6]. In each structure the number of sections is determined on the basis that the mean value of the feature with 99% probability shall be inside a confidence interval of ± 0.1 for the radii and ± 0.5 for interparticle distance. Volume fractions up to 30% are considered. The sizes in this paper are dimensionless but could be referred to as microns.

This paper covers the correlations between spatial and planar interparticle distances and radii distribution for uniform random distributed spheres with radii following a Gauss distribution. The analysis with all five distribution types will be published in [7].

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN 3D SPHERE RADII AND 2D PROFILE RADII

For sphere radii following a Gauss distribution about 30 different simulations are made, covering a broad spectrum of distribution parameters as they will occur in practical applications. The probability density function for Gauss distributed sphere radii R, is;

$$f_3(R) = \frac{1}{\sigma_G \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(R - \mu_G)^2}{2\sigma_G^2}\right) \tag{1}$$

where the mean value, μ_G , and the standard deviation, σ_G , are distribution parameters for the 3D sphere radii, as index 3 indicate in Eqn (1).

Fig. 2 presents appearance of spherical profiles on a plane section in a simulated structure together with corresponding probability density function of profile radii, r, for a structure with $\mu_G = 15$ and $\sigma_G = \sqrt{5}$.

Figure 2: (a) Profiles from a planar section in a simulated structure, (b) Probability density curve and histogram for the profile radii.

The profile radii density function obviously does not follow a Gauss distribution function, Fig. 2b, as its counterparts in 3D. It is therefore necessary to find another continuous function that describe the profile distribution, for correlating the plane profile radii to the spatial sphere radii. The extreme value function, Eqn (2), describes with good accuracy the broad spectrum of profile radii distributions that appear from sectioning the different simulations.

$$f_2(r) = \frac{1}{B_G} \left[\exp\left(\frac{r - A_G}{B_G}\right) \exp\left\{-\exp\left(\frac{r - A_G}{B_G}\right)\right\} \right] \quad (2)$$

For the two sets of distribution parameters, (μ_G, σ_G) for the Gauss distribution and (A_G, B_G) for the extreme value function, correlation maps have been created that relates 2D profile radii distribution to 3D sphere radii distribution, Fig. 3. There is a simple linear

Figure 3: Correlation between 2D and 3D size parameters (a) μ_G and A_G , (b) var_G and B_G .

correlation between the location parameter for the profile radii and the mean value for the sphere radii, which is independent of the standard deviation of the sphere radii, Fig. 3a. Correlation between shape parameter for profile radii and standard deviation for sphere radii is dependent of the mean value of sphere radii, but for each μ_G there seems to exist a linear correlation between the variance of sphere radii and shape parameter of profile radii, Fig. 3b. The simple relations indicate that it is possible, through numerical analysis, to find a continuous function that describe the profile density with a good accuracy.

Plotting the 2D distribution parameters, A_G and B_G , as functions of each other gives another correlation map, Fig. 4. The horizontal lines represent different μ_G and the vertical lines

Figure 4: Correlation between 2D and 3D size parameters for sphere radii distributed after a Gauss distribution.

different var_G , with a succession of the lines that correspond to the succession of the 3D distribution parameters. The solid lines are calculated by a least square method for points inside each category and dashed lines are drawn through the one point in the categories with a slope equal to the average value of the over and underlying line. A category represent either constant μ_G or constant var_G . Correlation map from Fig. 4 is an efficient tool to get an estimate of the 3D radii distribution parameters if the 2D radii distribution is known, then more accurate results can be gained using Fig. 3.

Similar correlation maps have been designed, besides the Gauss distribution, for constant, uniform random, Poisson and lognormal distribution of sphere radii, and a procedure for separating these 3D radii distributions from each other, using only the profile radii distributions, has been developed [7]. If a sphere radii distribution follows one of the five distribution functions it is possible with the correlation maps to find the 3D radii distribution parameters from the 2D radii distribution.

As a test five structures, one for each radii distribution, were simulated with almost similar distribution parameters, to see if it was possible to distinguish between the different distribution types, which was easy. The accuracy of the correlation maps is checked by calculating the statistical moments for the actual simulated sphere radii and the sphere radii predicted from the profile radii, and then by comparing them, Table1. The difference between the moments are all within an acceptable error.

Table 1: Statistical moments for actual and calculated sphere radii

	μ	σ	variance	skewness	kurtosis
Actual	17.0	2.6	6.9	-0.1	0.2
Calculated	16.9	2.7	7.1	0.0	0.0

CORRELATION BETWEEN 3D AND 2D INTERPARTICLE DISTANCES

Interparticle distance or nearest neighbour distance is the shortest distance between adjacent spherical inclusions in 3D or spherical profiles in 2D respectively. The 3D interparticle distances provide valuable information about the composites spatial composition, and are therefore of great interest. There are however, no expressions that can give the spatial interparticle distance distribution for a structure with inclusions of a given size. If the size of the inclusions is neglected and each inclusion treated as a point it is possible to give an estimate of the interparticle distance distribution [3], but with increasing inclusion size this estimate becomes less useful. The second type of accessible expressions is the mean nearest neighbour distances, which say as much or as little as the numerical density or volume fraction. A method for finding the spatial interparticle distances distribution is to relate it to its counterparts on plane sections and create correlation maps, similar to the radii correlation maps in the previous section.

An ideal solution for correlating the spatial and planar features is to create correlation maps between two functions that describe the 3D and the 2D interparticle distance distributions respectively, for all types of structures containing spherical inclusions. The influence of the inclusion radii is however so significant that different types of radii distributions; Gauss, Poisson etc, result in different correlation maps. Distinguishing between different radii distributions, and by that different correlation maps, are done on basis of sphere radii analysis, described in previous section. Only simulations with sphere radii following Gauss distributions are presented in this paper.

Fig. 5 show the 3D interparticle distance distribution together with the interparticle distance distribution appearing on plane sections in a structure with Gauss distributed sphere radii, $\mu_G = 15$, $\sigma_G = \sqrt{5}$.

Figure 5: (a) 3D interparticle distance distribution, (b) 2D interparticle distance distribution for a simulation with Gauss distributed sphere radii

Even if the shape of the 3D and 2D distribution is of the same type a direct correlation is not possible and it is necessary to find two functions that describe either of the features with acceptable accuracy. The functions must contain the numerical density of inclusions as a parameter, because the interinclusion distances, opposite the radii distribution, are dependent on the number of inclusions/profiles inside an examined volume/area. The functions used to describe the features have both the shape of a lognormal distribution function, where the numerical density, in 3D and 2D respectively, is a part of the shape parameter. Simulations with identical size distribution parameters, but different numerical densities, result in inter-

particle distribution curves with the same location but different shape. A decrease in the numerical density gives a wider curve, which is due to an increase in the shape parameter for a lognormal distribution function, why the numerical density is inverse proportional to the shape parameter. The 3D interparticle distance, D , is described by Eqn (3)

$$f_3(D) = \frac{1}{(\alpha_G/N_V) D \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(D) - \beta_G)^2}{2(\alpha_G/N_V)^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where index 3 indicate its 3D characteristics and α_G, β_G are variable parameters. On plane sections are the interparticle distances, d , described in Eqn (4)

$$f_2(d) = \frac{1}{(a_G/N_A) d \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(d) - b_G)^2}{2(a_G/N_A)^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

where a_G, b_G as α_G, β_G are variable parameters depending of numerical density and inclusion size.

Correlation maps are created between location parameters β_G, b_G and shape parameters α_G, a_G because the two functions, describing the spatial and planar features, are of the same type.

Figure 6: Correlation between 2D and 3D interparticle distances parameters (a) β_G and b_G , (b) α_G and a_G .

The location of the 3D interparticle distance distribution curve is almost identical to the corresponding curve from plane sections, Fig. 5, which results in a correlation where β_G and b_G are nearly equal to each other, Fig. 6a. For the shape parameters the correlation is not as simple, because α_G and a_G are divided by the numerical density, which is larger on plane sections, N_A , than in a spatial structure, N_V . The correlation map is a linear $\log - \log$ correlation, Fig. 6b.

Using the correlation maps in Fig. 6 to predict a composites spatial composition require knowledge of the spatial numerical density, N_V . This feature is easily calculated for structures containing spherical inclusions using the classical stereology [1] et.al, but some inaccuracies are present in these expressions. To avoid this, the expression for the spatial interparticle distances, Eqn (3), is changed to contain the plane numerical density instead of the spatial and the shape parameter α_G is changed to γ_G , Eqn (5). The functions are identical because

$\alpha_G/N_V = \gamma_G/N_A = \text{constant}$, the only change is the value of the shape parameter.

$$f_3(D) = \frac{1}{(\gamma_G/N_A) D \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(D) - \beta_G)^2}{2(\gamma_G/N_A)^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7 present the correlation map between the new spatial shape parameter γ_G and the plane shape parameter a_G , the correlation between the location parameters is unchanged, Fig. 6a.

Figure 7: Correlation between the spatial parameter γ_G and the plane parameter a_G .

Instead of having a linear $\log - \log$ correlation there is a simple linear correlation between the 3D and 2D shape parameter. Correlations in Fig. 6b and Fig. 7 are both linear correlations which are due to the mutual correlation between the 3D and the 2D numerical density.

Two methods are developed for estimating the spatial interparticle distance distribution from corresponding feature on plane cross sections. From the plane interparticle distance distribution a_G and b_G are calculated, fitting the distribution to the function given in Eqn (3).

method 1 The spatial interparticle distance distribution is described in Eqn 3 where the parameters α_G and β_G are calculated using correlation maps in Fig. 6 and parameters a_G, b_G . The last unknown parameter, the numerical density, is calculated from classical stereological expressions.

method 2 Correlation maps in Fig. 6a and Fig. 7 are used to calculate parameters that describe the spatial interparticle distance distribution Eqn 5, using a_G and b_G . The numerical density in Eqn (5) is calculated on the plane sections, and the use of other stereological expressions is avoided.

Similar methods, with corresponding correlation maps, for determining spatial interparticle distance distribution have been designed, besides Gauss distributed sphere radii, for constant, uniform random, Poisson and lognormal distributed radii, [7]. The test examples mentioned in previous section were analysed for interparticle distance distribution, and statistical moments for the actual structure were compared to moments calculated from method 1 and 2, where only plane features were used to predict the spatial distribution parameters, Table 2.

Table 2: Statistical moments for the actual and calculated interparticular distance.

	μ	σ	variance	skewness	kurtosis
Actual	37.3	4.2	17.7	0.2	0.2
Method 1	37.6	4.4	19.7	0.4	0.2
Method 2	37.6	4.4	19.0	0.4	0.2

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A simulation analysis for determination of spatial interparticle distances and radii distribution of spherical particles from microscopic images of composite cross sections has been performed. Correlation maps and functions, that relate spatial and plane features, has been designed for a relatively broad spectrum of size parameters. A method to distinguish between different sphere radii distributions from features measured on plane sections has been developed, and is fundamental for determination of the spatial size and distances parameters. Correlation maps and functions for sphere radii following a Gauss distribution have been considered in this paper and results from a simulated example are presented, with good agreement between actual and calculated spatial interparticle distance and sphere radii distribution.

For all the simulations the inclusions are distributed uniformly random in space (hard-core), and to be able to use the correlations is it essential that the real spherical radii distribution can be described with one of the five mentioned functions.

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